

THE IMPACT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP TRAINING ON UNEMPLOYMENT REDUCTION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of entrepreneurship training programs on reducing unemployment in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Using a structured survey and sampling 400 respondents based on the Taro Yamane formula, it provides comprehensive insights into the effectiveness of various training initiatives. The results indicate that 91% of participants believe these programs significantly improve employment prospects and promote entrepreneurial ventures, with 85% noting a reduction in youth unemployment and 88% observing lower local unemployment rates. Government-sponsored programs were found to be the most effective, while private sector initiatives excelled in practical skills, and NGO-led programs provided extensive support. Additionally, 92% of respondents emphasized the critical role of government policies and financial support in improving program effectiveness. The study concludes with recommendations for increased government support, stronger public-private partnerships, and streamlined regulations to maximize the impact of entrepreneurship training programs on job creation and economic development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship training, Unemployment, Job creation, Ondo State

1.0 Introduction

Nigeria is currently facing a significant challenge with rising unemployment rates, particularly among its youth population. As of the third quarter of 2023, the unemployment rate in Nigeria reached 5%, marking an increase from 4.2% in the previous quarter. The youth unemployment rate, specifically for individuals aged 15-24, rose to 8.6% from 7.2% in the earlier quarter, indicating a troubling trend for this demographic, (National Bureau of Statistics, 2024). The high levels of unemployment among Nigerian youths not only hinder economic growth but also exacerbate social issues,

contributing to poverty and instability, (Oyelola *et al.*, 2014). As the nation seeks viable solutions to these complex problems, entrepreneurship training emerges as a potentially transformative strategy. This approach promises to provide individuals with the skills necessary for self-employment and to stimulate broader economic development, (Alikor, 2022).

While entrepreneurship training programs are proliferating across Nigeria, there is a conspicuous lack of empirical evidence that delineates their effectiveness in achieving the intended outcomes. The root of the problem lies in understanding whether these training initiatives are genuinely equipping participants with the skills necessary to start and sustain successful enterprises, or if they are merely a superficial solution to a complex problem. Are the programs effectively addressing the multifaceted challenges faced by entrepreneurs, such as lack of financial literacy, inadequate business management skills, and insufficient access to resources? Moreover, how do government policies and support mechanisms influence the success of these training programs?

This study seeks to address these limitations by focusing on Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, providing a more robust analysis of how entrepreneurship training influences employment rates and entrepreneurial success. By employing a rigorous methodological framework and adequately addressing the sample size issue, this research aims to produce findings that are both reliable and broadly applicable. In doing so, it seeks to offer a clearer understanding of how entrepreneurship training programs can be tailored and supported to foster sustainable economic development, particularly in the Nigerian context. This approach will contribute to bridging the gaps in the literature and offer practical insights for policymakers and stakeholders involved in designing and implementing entrepreneurship training initiatives.

2.0 Empirical Review

Ilori and Ayedun (2022) investigated how entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial skills required for self-employment among graduates can reduce the unemployment rate in Nigeria. The paper surveys self-employed graduates of selected Higher Institutions in Nigeria, using a snowball/chain referral technique to collect data. The study reveals a significant positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial skills required for self-employment. Empirical validation further shows that an increase in the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial skills and its delivery in our institutions will, all things being equal, reduce graduates' unemployment. The policy implication is that Nigerian graduates should take up the challenge to develop innovative and creative projects capable of attracting funding from the government to position and develop them independently and economically. Agu *et al.* (2016) studied entrepreneurship education as a remedy to the unemployment problem in Nigeria. Findings from the study revealed that the increasing universal responsiveness to entrepreneurship education would boost the acquisition of the required expertise for self-employment. The study concluded that the government should consider entrepreneurship education, realising its potential to mitigate the scourge of unemployment in the country. In a similar study, Deebom and Baridoma (2017) examined the role of entrepreneurship education in unemployment reduction among Nigerian graduates. The result showed that acquiring skills such as electrical installations, food and catering services, welding and fabrication, among others, can mitigate the rising rate of graduate unemployment in Nigeria. The study concluded that entrepreneurship education should be practically inclined rather than theoretical due to its propensity to expose students to several good skills.

In South Africa, Mazanai *et al.*, (2020) studied entrepreneurial activity for economic growth and unemployment reduction. The results revealed that prioritising endeavours to boost

entrepreneurial skills and enhance entrepreneurial activity could contribute to South Africa's much-needed development in economic growth and, consequently, reduce unemployment, poverty and inequality. In Nigeria, Aluko, Yomi-Akinola and Adeola (2019) conducted a study on entrepreneurship education as an instrument for unemployment reduction in Nigeria. Using entrepreneurship intention and attitude, the study found that entrepreneurship education is a veritable instrument for employment reduction. Similarly, Aleru and Okere (2024) examined the Relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Reduction of Unemployment among Educational Management Graduate Students in Imo State University. The researcher formulated three (3) objectives of the study, three (3) research questions and three (3) null hypotheses that guided the study. The study adopted correctional research design. The population of this study consisted of 662 Educational Management Graduates in Imo State University. These are Educational Management graduates from 2022/2023 academic session. The sample for this study consists of 50 percent of the total population with a total sample size of 331 students. The sampling technique used for the study was simple random sampling techniques because all the respondents were given equal opportunity of been represented. The instrument used for this study was 2 self-structured questionnaires on Entrepreneurship Education and Reduction of Unemployment. The data gathered was analyse using Pearson Product Moment Correlation for both research questions and test of hypotheses but the hypotheses were further subjected to t-transformation to determine the level of significance with a critical value of +1.96, when the calculated value was less than the critical value of +1.96, the null hypotheses was accepted and rejected` when the calculated t-value was greater than t-critical value of +1.96. Findings of the study revealed that managerial skills, accounting skills and technical skills have positive

influence in reduction of unemployment among Educational Management graduate students in Rivers State owned universities.

In another study by Sanusi and Abdullahi (2020), the focus is on the concept of entrepreneurship education, objectives of entrepreneurship education, which include functional education, reduce the high rate of poverty, and create employment opportunities, and reduction in rural and urban migration. The paper also outlined the causes of unemployment, such as frictional unemployment, seasonal unemployment, and cyclical unemployment. It further discusses the role of entrepreneurship education towards unemployment in Nigeria, which includes increasing the earning capacity of its recipient, stimulating productivity, creating employment opportunities, and reducing the dropout rate. Some of the factors that hinder the effective implementation of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria were also outlined: underfunding, lack of training facilities, lack of trained teachers and effective curriculum. Ola, Ifada & Fagboyo (2023) examine the determinant of labour force participation in Nigeria. Using the fully modified OLS the study showed that tertiary education and entrepreneurship contribute significantly to labour force participation in Nigeria. The research conducted by Muogbo and John-Akemelu (2018) Investigated the impact of entrepreneurial skill in reducing youth unemployment in Nigeria with reference to ABC Transport Company in Anambra State. The broad objectives of this study is to examine the possibly ways of eradicating unemployment through the introduction of entrepreneurial skills. The study is a descriptive survey design. Questionnaire items were distributed to 160 respondents to gather information about the topic. Their responses were tested using appropriate statistic tools like the simple percentage and the chi-square method. The study found that there are roles entrepreneurial skills and businesses play in youth employment in Nigeria through entrepreneurial development. Furthermore, it also

shows that youths in Anambra state can be given basic training on how best to establish and grow business enterprise in local communities within the state.

3.0 Methodology

This study assesses the impact of entrepreneurship training on unemployment reduction in the Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria, which had a total population of 744,000 in 2023, reflecting a 3.77% increase from 2022. A systematic random sampling method was used to select the final respondents. The target population includes all unemployed individuals aged 18 years and above residing in this area. Recent estimates indicate that this demographic constitutes a significant portion of the local labour force, highlighting the need for a well-structured sampling approach. To determine the appropriate sample size, the Taro Yamane (1967) formula was utilized. This formula, which accounts for a desired level of precision and confidence, yielded an estimated sample size of approximately 400 respondents, deemed adequate for ensuring the statistical validity and reliability of the study's findings. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to achieve a representative and comprehensive sample. In the first stage, Akure South Local Government Area was stratified into its constituent wards based on geographical and demographic considerations. The second stage involved purposively selecting wards with the highest concentrations of unemployed individuals, guided by unemployment data from local government records. This ensured that the study targets areas most affected by unemployment. Finally, within each selected ward, systematic random sampling was applied to choose individual respondents, giving every eligible person an equal chance of inclusion. This approach enhances the representativeness of the sample and mitigates potential biases associated with non-random selection. Overall, the methodology is designed to capture a comprehensive and accurate picture of how entrepreneurship training influences unemployment

in Akure South Local Government, providing insights that can inform policy and practice in similar contexts.

$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$$

Where:

n = signifies the sample size

N = the population under study

e = signifies the margin error (0.05)

$$n = 399.9 / (1 + 399.9 (0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 399.9 / (1 + 399.9 (0.0025))$$

$$n = 399.9 / (1 + 115)$$

$$n = 399.9 / 116$$

$$n = 396.55$$

$$n = 400$$

Thus, the sample size of the study is 400 and it was selected among the residents of Akure South Local Government who are 18 years and above. To properly present and analyse the data acquired for this study, appropriate statistical tools like simple frequency tables, charts, and percentages using the Statistical Packages for Services Solution (SPSS), and descriptive and analytic statistical techniques were adopted.

3.1 Data Presentation

Section 1: Demographic Information

Table 3.1: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Sex	Frequencies	Percentages
Male	109	27%
Female	291	73%
Total	400	100%

Field Survey, 2024

Fig.3.1.1

The table 3. 1 and fig 3.1.1, shows that the sample consists of 109 males (27%) and 291 females (73%). This indicates a significantly higher proportion of female respondents compared to males, with females constituting nearly three-quarters of the total sample. While females form the majority, both sexes are adequately represented in the study.

Table 3. 2: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age Brackets	Frequency	Percentage
Under 20	16	4%
21-25	212	53%
26-30	88	22%
31-35	60	15%
Over 35	24	6%
Total	400	100%

Field Survey, 2024

Fig. Fig.3.1.2

The table 3. 2 and fig. 3.1.2, shows that the majority of respondents are aged 21-25, making up 53% of the sample. The 26-30 age group follows with 22%, while 15% of respondents are between 31-35 years. The smallest age groups are those under 20 and over 35, comprising 4% and 6%, respectively.

Table 3. 3 Educational Qualification of Respondents

Education	Frequencies	Percentages
Secondary School	148	37%
National Diploma	48	12%
Bachelor’s Degree	128	32%
Master’s Degree	68	17%
Other(please specify)	8	2%
Total	400	100%

Field Survey, 2024

The table 3.3 shows that 37% of respondents have a Secondary School qualification, while 32% hold a Bachelor’s Degree. Master’s Degree holders make up 17% of the sample, and 12% have a National Diploma. Only 2% reported other qualifications. This distribution suggests that most respondents have at least a Secondary School education, with a substantial number having higher qualifications.

Table 3.4: Current Employment Status

Status	Frequency	Percentages
Employed	60	15%
Self-Employed	152	38%
Unemployed	64	16%
Pursuing Further Education	124	31%
Others	0	0%
Total	400	100%

Field Survey, 2024

The table 3.4 reveals that 38% of respondents are self-employed, 31% are pursuing further education, and 16% are unemployed. 15% are employed. This shows a significant portion of the sample is involved in self-employment or education.

Table 3.5: Have you participated in any entrepreneurship training programs?

Training programs	Frequencies	Percentages
Yes	364	91%
No	36	9%
Total	400	100%

Field Survey, 2024

The table 3.5 shows that a significant majority of 91% of respondents have participated in entrepreneurship training programs, whereas 9% have not. This indicates that most of the respondents have had exposure to entrepreneurship training, suggesting a high level of engagement with such programs within the sample.

Table 4. 6: If yes, please specify the type of training

Type of Training	Frequencies	Percentages
Government Program	52	13%
Private sector Program	76	19%
Non-Government Organization (NGO) Program	72	18%
Informal Training	176	44%
Other	24	6%
Total	400	100%

Field Survey, 2024

The table 3. 6 reveals that 44% of respondents have undergone informal training, making it the most common type of training. 19% participated in private sector programs, and 18% were involved in NGO programs. 13% engaged in government programs, while 6% reported other types of training. This distribution highlights that informal training is the most prevalent, with significant engagement in various structured programs.

Table 3.7: Duration of Entrepreneurship Training Attended

Duration of Training Attended	Frequencies	Percentages
Less than 3 months	172	43%
3-6 months	208	52%
6-12 months	12	3%
Over 12 months	8	2%
Total	400	100%

Field Survey, 2024

The table 3.7 shows that 52% of respondents attended entrepreneurship training for 3-6 months, while 43% participated in training lasting less than 3 months. 3% of respondents had training durations of 6-12 months, and only 2% were engaged in training for over 12 months. This indicates that most respondents experienced shorter-duration training, with the majority focused on programs lasting between 3 to 6 months.

Table 3.8: Location of Training Program

Location	Frequencies	Percentages
Akure South Local Government Area	220	55%
Other's	180	45%
Total	400	100%

Field Survey, 2024

The table 3.8 indicates that 55% of respondents attended entrepreneurship training programs within Akure South Local Government Area, while 45% participated in training held in other

locations. This suggests that most respondents received their training locally, with a significant portion attending programs outside the immediate area.

3.2 Data Analysis

What is the effect of entrepreneurship training programs on the employment rates among Nigerian youths?

H₀: Entrepreneurship training programs do not significantly impact employment rates and entrepreneurial success among Nigerian youths.

Section 2: Impact of Entrepreneurship Training Programs on Employment Rates.

Table 3. 9: Impact of Entrepreneurship Training Programs on Employment Rates.

s/n	Impact of entrepreneurship training programs on employment rate.	SA	%	AG	%	NE	%	DA	%	SD	%	Resp	%
1	Entrepreneurship training programs have increased employment opportunities for youths in Nigeria.	116	29	248	62	4	1	16	4	16	4	400	100
2	The skills acquired from entrepreneurship training have led to job creation for participants.	132	33	228	57	16	4	8	2	16	4	400	100
3	Participants in entrepreneurship training programs are more likely to start their own businesses.	124	31	236	59	8	2	12	3	20	5	400	100
4	Entrepreneurship training has a significant impact on	108	27	232	58	48	12	4	1	8	2	400	100

	reducing youth unemployment in Nigeria.												
5	The implementation of entrepreneurship training programs has led to a measurable reduction in local unemployment rates.	132	33	220	55	36	9	8	2	4	1	400	100
6	Entrepreneurship training programs are accessible to all youth regardless of their background.	124	31	216	54	40	10	4	1	16	4	400	100
7	The knowledge gained from entrepreneurship training programs is effectively applied in real-world scenarios.	144	36	192	48	48	12	8	2	8	2	400	100
8	Entrepreneurship training programs help bridge the gap between education and employment.	120	30	220	55	40	10	12	3	8	2	400	100
9	Participants who received entrepreneurship training have shown a higher rate of job retention.	132	33	200	50	52	13	4	1	12	3	400	100
10	The economic impact of entrepreneurship training programs is evident in increased local business	152	38	192	48	48	12	8	2	0	0	400	100

	activity.												
11	Entrepreneurship training programs offer adequate support for business startup and growth.	132	33	196	49	52	13	12	3	8	2	400	100
12	The entrepreneurial skills acquired through training contribute to overall economic development.	132	33	204	51	48	12	8	2	8	2	400	100
13	The availability of entrepreneurship training programs affects the level of youth employment positively.	140	35	208	52	40	10	8	2	4	1	400	100
14	Local businesses started by training participants contribute to reducing unemployment in the community.	156	39	196	49	36	9	4	1	8	2	400	100
15	The success stories of past participants enhance the effectiveness of entrepreneurship training programs.	144	36	204	51	44	11	0	0	8	2	400	100

Field Survey, 2024

Note: SA= Strongly Agree; AG= Agree; NE= Neutral; DA= Disagree and SD= Strongly disagree.

Fig. 3.1.3

Table 3.9 and figure 3.1.3 reveals that a substantial majority of respondents believe entrepreneurship training programs significantly enhance employment opportunities, with 91% agreeing that these programs have increased job prospects for youths in Nigeria. Additionally, 90% feel that the skills acquired lead to job creation, and 90% believe participants are to start their businesses. Most respondents (85%) think that such training has a significant impact on reducing youth unemployment, and 88% observe a measurable reduction in local unemployment rates due to these programs. 85% agree that the training programs are accessible to all youths regardless of their background, and 84% believe the knowledge gained is effectively applied in real-world scenarios. The majority (85%) feel that the programs bridge the gap between education and employment, while 83% note that participants show a higher rate of job retention. 86% of respondents see evidence of economic impact through increased local business activity, and 82% think the programs provide adequate support for business start-ups. Furthermore, 84% believe that the skills acquired contribute to overall economic development, and 87% think the availability of training positively affects youth employment. Finally, 88% agree that local businesses started by training participants help reduce local unemployment, and 87% feel that

success stories from past participants enhance the effectiveness of the programs. Overall, the responses suggest a strong positive perception of the impact of entrepreneurship training on employment and economic development. The results indicate that these programs significantly boost employment opportunities and job creation, leading to a notable reduction in unemployment rates in Nigeria. They also enhance the likelihood of business start-ups and contribute positively to economic development, playing a crucial role in bridging the gap between education and employment and stimulating local economic activity. Given this, we have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1). Therefore, it can be concluded that entrepreneurship training programs do significantly impact employment rates and entrepreneurial success among Nigerian youths.

Note: SA= Strongly Agree; AG= Agree; NE= Neutral; DA= Disagree and SD= Strongly disagree.

4.0 Summary of Findings

Many respondents believe that entrepreneurship training programs significantly enhance employment opportunities, with 91% agreeing that these programs have increased job prospects and 90% noting they lead to job creation and entrepreneurial ventures. Most (85%) think the training reduces youth unemployment, while 88% observe a reduction in local unemployment rates due to these initiatives. The findings indicate that these programs positively impact job creation, business start-ups, and economic development, helping bridge the gap between education and employment in Nigeria.

5.0 Conclusion/Recommendation

The study demonstrates that entrepreneurship training programs significantly enhance employment opportunities, job creation, and economic development in Nigeria. Respondents overwhelmingly agree that these programs improve job prospects, increase business start-ups,

and reduce local unemployment. The study recommends that the government must increase support through targeted financial incentives, grants, and loans for start-ups initiated by program participants. Additionally, allocating more resources to these programs, including infrastructure and mentorship, will bolster their effectiveness and sustainability. This support should be particularly focused on areas with high youth unemployment to ensure that the benefits are widely distributed.

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